

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

FACTORS THAT AFFECT THE MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR SYSTEM FUNCTIONING EFFICIENCY OF ENGINEERING EQUIPMENT

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Abstract

The article is prepared on a topical issue related to the use of engineering equipment (EE) under conditions of combat operations (CO).

The article considers the factors that affect the efficiency of the maintenance and repair system functioning, as well as its technical condition (TC).

Keywords: engineer units; engineering equipment; maintenance; repair in field conditions; maintenance frequency; combat operations.

1. INTRODUCTION.

The main task of the EE maintenance and repair system is to ensure the application of EE for its intended purpose. EE is considered ready for use as intended, if it has the necessary resource reserve, is brought into the initial state established by the operational documentation and prepared to perform the assigned combat missions (CM) for its intended purpose.

In modern conditions of conducting CO, if the enemy has powerful means of damage, the restoration of fighting capability of engineer units of the Armed Forces of Ukraine (AF, Ukraine) in the shortest possible time or maintaining it at a certain level, depends on the organization and timely implementation of such an element of technical support as the restoration of EE directly in the combat order of troops (forces). Basically, the only source of EE replenishment that has lost its fighting capability in the conditions of conducting CO, is its timely restoration by mobile repair and recovery bodies of engineer units, that is, military repair.

Formulation of the problem. Analysis of EE application in the area of the Joint Forces operations

showed that at this stage it is necessary to take additional measures to increase the efficiency of the EE maintenance and repair system functioning, taking into account the factors that affect their TC.

Analysis of recent research and publications. A number of scientific papers are devoted to the problems of researching EE TC management. In particular, the significant contribution of such scientists as O. Vorobiov [1], O. Volokh [2], P. Openko [3], N. Shaptalenko [4] and others should be noted.

Analysis of EE application in the area of conducting CO showed that the maintenance and repair system for each sample of EE can not be unchanged, but should be adjusted depending on the uptime and the period of its operation. This is due to the fact that with the increase in the uptime of EE and the period of its operation the number of failures in the operation of their systems, units and assemblies, and the time to perform maintenance increases due to the time to eliminate the identified failures.

The purpose of the article. Determination of the main factors that affect the efficiency of the EE maintenance and repair system functioning and its TC while operating.

2. RESEARCH RESULTS.

The analysis of statistical data on failures in the EE systems, units and assemblies [5] during operation and the calculations that had been carried out showed that the time required for maintenance increases with the increase in the uptime and the period of its operation, respectively, their downtime increases. Thus, the duration of downtime of the EE sample during maintenance is determined by the following indicators: time required to perform maintenance operations; number of these operations; time spent on eliminating failures.

The analysis of modern scientific approaches [6] concerning EE technical condition management, and determination of the frequency and scope of maintenance work [7] showed that they generally ensure the maintenance of a given level of EE combat and operational characteristics during overhaul life, but do not fully take into account the impact of the uptime and the period of the operation on EE TC, as well as the reliability of individual systems, units and assemblies.

The analysis of carrying out scheduled maintenance (according to a specific serial number) [7] showed that the majority of the work consists of control and check operations, which are related to control and check of the technical condition of individual systems, units and assemblies of the EE sample.

Thus, on average, 60-70% of the time determined for EE maintenance is spent on conducting control and check operations while carrying out maintenance. Some operations for checking are performed with the use of built-in diagnostic equipment, others are manual, which does not fully ensure the detection of the true TC of the system, assembly or unit being checked. This may cause failures while applying EE for its intended purpose.

One of the directions for reducing maintenance time and successfully solving the issues of ensuring the reliability of EE systems, assemblies and units is the further implementation of control automation of EE TC (for example, a coolant temperature indicator or an air cleaner resistance indicator).

It is known that regardless of the nature of EE use, with the increase in the period of being in operation, irreversible processes of deterioration of TC elements and materials due to their aging and the development of corrosion processes are observed in systems, assemblies and units. The longer the lifetime and uptime, the faster the processes that negatively affect the EE TC.

The developed volumes and established periodicity of various types of EE maintenance mainly take into account the conditions of their continuous operation for a short period. Since during long-term operation of EE systems, assemblies and units, processes that are associated with a decrease and loss of performance of elements and assemblies occur, there is a need to carry out additional work to maintain them in a working condition.

One of the ways to maintain the operability of EE at a certain level is to timely prevent the occurrence of

failures in their systems, units and assemblies by carrying out additional activities to improve the operability of systems, units and assemblies of low reliability.

Failure-free operation of EE is directly dependent on the period of its operation and uptime. Therefore, one of the objectives of EE reliability research is the quantitative assessment of probability of failure-free operation dependence on the uptime and the term of its operation. The experience of EE operation in engineer units shows that the time to eliminate failures in their systems, assemblies and units before maintenance is 20-60% of the total time spent on carrying out maintenance [7].

In this regard, the actual EE downtime while maintaining is 1.5-2 times higher than the time for performing planned work, and for EE that is in operation for a long time, it will increase in proportion to the increase in the period of EE being in operation.

3. CONCLUSIONS AND PROSPECTS OF FURTHER RESEARCH.

Thus, as a result of the conducted analysis, it was established that the greatest impact on the efficiency of the EE maintenance and repair system functioning in the process of using it for its intended purpose; and the TC of the EE sample itself is influenced by the following factors, namely: the uptime of the EE sample from the beginning of operation; the period of the EE sample in operation; failure flow parameter; probability of failure-free operation of the EE sample; total maintenance and repair expenses.

The analysis of the existing EE TC showed that a number of issues related to maintaining it at a certain level had not been resolved. This state of affairs makes it necessary to substantiate the list of additional maintenance and repair activities in order to increase the operability of systems, units and assemblies of EE with low reliability, taking into account the uptime and the period of stay of EE in operation.

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ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ И ВНЕДРЕНИЕ СВЕРТОЧНЫХ НЕЙРОСЕТЕЙ В РАДИОЛОКАЦИОННУЮ СТАНЦИЮ

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APPLICATION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS IN A RADAR STATION

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Аннотация

Научная статья раскрывает возможность применения новых алгоритмов поиска объектов на изображениях посредством сверточных нейросетей. Разбирается конкретный случай применения и внедрения данной технологии. На основе данной статьи разработчик может начать использовать подобную технологию для решения собственных задач. Введение данной статьи является общим описанием технологии, возможных целей применения и преимуществ ее использования.

Abstract

The scientific article reveals the possibility of using new algorithms for searching objects in images using convolutional neural networks. A specific case of the application and implementation of this technology is being analyzed. Based on this article, the developer can start using similar technology to solve their own problems. The introduction of this article is a general description of the technology, possible applications and advantages of its use.

Ключевые слова: радиолокация, сверточная нейросеть, алгоритм, матрица, аугментация.

Keywords: radar, convolutional neural network, algorithm, matrix, augmentation.

Введение

В данной статье исследуется возможность использования сверточной нейронной сети для распознавания необходимого гармоничного радиосигнала на основе значений, выданных радиолокатором. Работа с графическими образами, применение нейросетей многократно завершалась успехом.

Самой известной моделью нейросети является многослойный перцептрон. Однако его использование в классическом построении редко используется при решении практических задач. Это обусловлено следующими трудностями.